

A Component of Click-Evoked Otoacoustic Emissions Evoked due to Perturbation of Nonlinear Force in a Cochlear Model

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Abstract. An analytic solution for stimulus-frequency otoacoustic emissions derived from the nonlinear cochlear model was presented at the Mechanics of Hearing meeting in 2022 [1]. Here, we describe how to use this solution for click-evoked otoacoustic emissions (CEOAEs) derived from the same model. The cochlear model is nonlinear because the feedback force, which is included in the model, is transformed by a sigmoidal nonlinearity proportional to the 2nd-order Boltzmann function. Our solution of the model equations extracts the nonlinear component of this feedback force and denotes this term the "nonlinear force". We showed that for SFOAEs the wavelets reflected from the irregularities perturb this nonlinear force. This perturbation yields an OAE component, which becomes significant as the simulated basilar membrane (BM) input/output (I/O) function approaches its compression knee (above about 20 dB SPL in the model). At low intensities (<20 dB SPL), SFOAEs and CEOAEs derived from the cochlear model are equivalent. As the intensity increases, the CEOAE amplitude increases and finally saturates. The CEOAE phase slope is intensity invariant. The amplitude saturation and phase intensity invariance of these CEOAEs is in contrast with the stimulus intensity effect on SFOAEs derived from the same model. For these SFOAEs, the component due to perturbation of the nonlinear force destructively interferes with the component due to linear reflection from irregularities. In addition, because the component due to perturbation of the nonlinear force has a slightly steeper phase slope than the component due to linear reflection, the amplitude fine-structure of SFOAE changes, and at some frequencies the SFOAE amplitude declines with increasing level. In other words, rather than just saturation as in CEOAEs, the SFOAE amplitude may decline and the SFOAE phase slope becomes shallower. For CEOAEs the component due to perturbation of the nonlinear force and the component due to linear reflection have similar phase slopes. These phase slopes become shallower as the intensity increases. However, the superposition of these two components yields CEOAE with a phase slope that is steeper than the phase slope of these two components. In conclusion, SFOAEs and CEOAEs derived from the same cochlear model differ as the intensity increases above the compression knee in the BM I/O function. The analytical solution can provide insight into the causes of the observed differences.

INTRODUCTION

Click-evoked otoacoustic emissions (CEOAEs) and stimulus-frequency OAEs (SFOAEs) are assumed to be primarily generated by linear reflection from mechanical irregularities in the organ of Corti [2, 3, 4, 5]. The same generation mechanism is assumed because experimental studies have shown that SFOAEs and CEOAEs are almost equivalent across stimulus intensities. For example, Kalluri and Shera [6] compared SFOAEs measured in humans for stimulus intensities ranging from 10 to 40 dB SPL with CEOAEs measured for click intensities ranging from 35 to 80 dB peSPL, Sisto *et al.* [7] measured SFOAEs in humans for probe intensities of 10 to 45 dB SPL and CEOAEs for 20 to 90 dB peSPL, and Charaziak and Shera [8] measured SFOAEs in gerbil for probe intensities of 20 to 60 dB SPL and CEOAEs for 35 to 75 dB peSPL. The last study also showed small differences between the SFOAEs and CEOAEs, especially at high stimulus intensities.

To study the mechanism of OAE generation in a nonlinear cochlear model composed of fluid-coupled oscillators, we presented analytic solutions for distortion-product OAEs (DPOAEs) [9] and for stimulus-frequency OAEs (SFOAEs) [1]. These solutions were obtained for the cochlear model with irregularities in the parameters affecting the BM impedance, so that the model would generate OAEs due to coherent reflection. In this paper, we show that the solution for SFOAEs can be used to analyze click-evoked OAEs (CEOAEs). In addition, we show that SFOAEs and CEOAEs derived from the model are equivalent at the lowest intensities but differ at higher intensities when the BM displacement reaches the compression knee in the BM I/O function.

METHODS

Analytical solution of the cochlear model for SFOAEs

We present an analytical solution of the model equations in the frequency domain by assuming that the stationary BM displacement [transversal displacement $\xi(x, t)$] in the time domain can be approximated by the truncated Fourier series

$$\xi(x, t) \approx \sum_{n=-N}^N \hat{\xi}_n(x) e^{in\omega_0 t}, \quad (1)$$

where ω_0 is the fundamental frequency which is "small enough that the input frequencies may be chosen as close as is desired to any finite set of real values" [10]; n are integers.

SFOAEs can be simulated by vector subtraction between the predicted ear-canal pressure in response to a pure tone for the cochlear model with irregularities and for the smooth cochlear model (without irregularities). Vencovský et al. [1] presented an analytical solution for such calculated SFOAEs (\hat{P}_{SFOAE}) in the nonlinear cochlear model; namely,

$$\hat{P}_{\text{SFOAE}} \propto \Delta \hat{\xi}_n^P(0) \approx - \int_0^L \hat{H}_n(0, s) \Delta \hat{U}_n^{\text{NL}}(s) ds + \sum_{j=2}^J \hat{\xi}_n^{P,j}(0), \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta \hat{\xi}_n^P(0)$ is the difference between BM displacements in the most basal BM segment for the cochlear model with irregularities and for the smooth cochlear model, $\hat{H}_n(0, s)$ is the Green's function of the integrodifferential kernel [Eq. (8) in [1]], which includes the BM parameters, hydrodynamical coupling between BM segments, and the linear part of the undamping feedback force $u(x) \hat{T}_n^{\text{TM}}(x) \hat{\xi}_n(x)$. The cochlear amplification is included in the term

$$\hat{U}_n(x) \equiv u(x) \frac{1}{T_0} \int_0^{T_0} S \left[\sum_{b=-N}^N \hat{t}_b^{\text{TM}}(x) \hat{\xi}_b(x) e^{ib\omega_0 t} \right] e^{-in\omega_0 t} dt, \quad (3)$$

where the transversal BM displacement $\hat{\xi}_n(x)$ is transferred into the shearing displacement $\hat{\eta}_n(x)$ between the tectorial membrane (TM) and the reticular lamina (RL) by the transfer function $\hat{T}_b^{\text{TM}}(x)$ (transfer function of a resonance circuit), the term $u(x)$ is a function controlling the gain, and $S[\cdot]$ is a nonlinear function proportional to the second order Boltzmann function (for details see [1, 10, 11]). To find an analytical solution for OAEs, Vetešník and Gummer [12] extracted the nonlinear part of the undamping feedback force $\hat{U}_n^{\text{NL}}(x)$ by subtracting the linear part of the undamping force $u(x) \hat{T}_n^{\text{TM}}(x) \hat{\xi}_n(x)$; i.e., the undamping force without the term $S[\cdot]$; namely,

$$\hat{U}_n^{\text{NL}}(x) \equiv u(x) \frac{1}{T_0} \int_0^{T_0} S \left[\sum_{b=-N}^N \hat{t}_b^{\text{TM}}(x) \hat{\xi}_b(x) e^{ib\omega_0 t} \right] e^{-in\omega_0 t} dt - u(x) \hat{T}_n^{\text{TM}}(x) \hat{\xi}_n(x). \quad (4)$$

$\Delta \hat{U}_n^{\text{NL}}(s)$ in Eq. (2) is the difference between the nonlinear force calculated for the model with irregularities and the nonlinear force calculated for the smooth cochlear model. We call this difference "the perturbation of the nonlinear force" [1, 9]. The term $-\int_0^L \hat{H}_n(0, s) \Delta \hat{U}_n^{\text{NL}}(s) ds$ in the solution for SFOAEs (denoted by the NL term in this paper), would therefore be missing if the model were linear; we call it the term due to perturbation of the nonlinear force [1]. The term $\sum_{j=2}^J \hat{\xi}_n^{P,j}(0)$ is due to the coherent reflection of the forward going traveling wave from irregularities (denoted by the CR component in this paper). This component must be obtained iteratively; for explanation, see [9] which implemented the approach described in [13].

To generate OAEs by coherent reflection, we must add mechanical irregularities into the BM impedance. We place the irregularities into the function $\tilde{u}(x)$ affecting the amount of undamping force. The irregularities were added in the form of Gaussian-distributed (white) noise; namely,

$$\tilde{u}(x) = u(x) + \Delta u(x), \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta u(x) = \varepsilon u(x)$ and $\varepsilon \approx \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$. Figure 1 shows that the irregularities are added into the BM segments at mid-frequencies. In this paper, OAEs were derived for $\sigma = 0.02$.

FIGURE 1. A: Irregularities added into the undamping feedback force. The arrows indicate the best frequencies of the BM segments obtained for 0 dB SPL. B: Impulse responses to clicks of various intensities derived in the model section tuned to 1740 Hz at 0 dB SPL.

Application of the solution for SFOAEs to CEOAEs

The analytical solution in Eq. (2) was obtained for a steady-state response. A linear system can be characterized by a transfer function, which is the Fourier transform of the impulse response. Because the cochlear model is nonlinear, using tools known for linear systems may be problematic. However, it has been shown in the experimental literature that responses of cochlear filters are equivalent if we measure them using steady-state tones, swept sines, or clicks [14]. The nonlinear forces needed to calculate the term $\Delta\hat{U}_n^{\text{NL}}(s)$ and the Green's function $\hat{H}_n(0, s)$ in Eq. (2) can be calculated by numerically solving the time-domain model equations [9] in Matlab. We used the Dormand-Prince method, which is a member of the Runge-Kutta family of ODE solvers. We divided the BM into 800 segments and used a sampling frequency of 600 kHz. The model responses to a click (see Fig. 1B) were for each BM segment converted into the frequency domain by the fast Fourier transform. $\hat{U}_n^{\text{NL}}(s)$, $\hat{H}_n(0, s)$, and $\hat{\xi}_n^{P,j}(0)$ in Eq. (2) at a given frequency were then constructed by taking the corresponding frequency bin from the spectrum calculated in every model section. By this method, we were able to calculate CEOAEs and their CR and NL components.

RESULTS

To verify the possibility of using the analytical solution for SFOAEs [Eq. (2)] to predict CEOAEs, Fig. 2A-1,2 depicts CEOAEs derived from the analytical solution and from numerical solution. The OAEs were derived from the displacement of the most basal BM segment $\Delta\hat{\xi}_\omega^P(0)$ expressed in dB relative to $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ a.u.; artificial units because the model is not calibrated to simulate BM displacement or acoustic pressure in the ear canal quantitatively. For the analytical solution, we used 11 iterations [$J = 11$ in Eq. (2)]. Amplitudes and phases of CEOAEs in Fig. 2A-1,2 show excellent agreement between the analytical and numerical solutions, which engenders confidence in the possibility of using the analytical solution for CEOAE analyses.

With confidence in the analytical solution in Eq. (2), we now analyze the individual CEOAE components present in the solution. The primary generation mechanism for CEOAEs is coherent reflection from mechanical irregularities. The reflected wavelets create the component denoted as CR. However, the wavelets generated due to reflection perturb the nonlinear force, which creates an additional CEOAE component denoted by NL. Figure 3 depicts the CR and NL components for the same stimulus parameters as in Fig. 2. The grey area indicates the region with data from Fig. 2. Notice that the overall CEOAE has a smaller dynamic range than the individual components. In addition, the components have a much more level variant phase than the resulting CEOAE.

Our aim is to compare CEOAEs, CR and NL components with SFOAEs and their components derived from the same cochlear model. Figure 2B,C,D shows input/output (I/O) functions of CEOAEs and SFOAEs at three different frequencies (indicated by the vertical dashed lines in Fig 2A-1,2). SFOAEs were presented in [1]. Figure 2E-G depict the BM displacement as a function of tone level; i.e., I/O functions of the cochlear model. CEOAEs and SFOAEs are evoked using different stimuli. For pure tones, we use sound pressure level (SPL) in dB to describe their intensity. For clicks, we calculate the peak amplitude of the click and describe click intensity in peak-equivalent SPL (peSPL). Kalluri and Shera [6] converted the click intensity from peSPL into "bandwidth-compensated" SPL and showed equivalence between transfer functions for CEOAEs and SFOAEs. They showed that the conversion depends on the click bandwidth. In our simulation, the click is an ideal click with a bandwidth larger than the frequency range of the cochlear model. We decided to empirically shift the CR component of CEOAEs in order to achieve visual

FIGURE 2. A-1,2: Amplitude and phase of CEOAEs derived from the cochlear model using a click stimulus of various levels. B,C,D: Input/output (I/O) functions showing amplitudes of CEOAEs, SFOAEs, and their CR and NL components derived from the analytical solution for various probe tone levels. The probe tone level of the click was shifted by subtracting 55 dB and the I/O functions of CEOAEs and their CR and NL components were decreased by 25 dB to achieve qualitative agreement between the CR component of CEOAE and the CR component of SFOAE. The I/O functions were simulated at frequencies 1740 Hz (B), 2350 Hz (C), and 3100 Hz (D) (vertical dashed lines in panel A-1). E,F,G: BM I/O functions simulated in the model segments tuned to the frequencies for the OAE I/O functions. The model segments were tuned to these frequencies at 0 dB SPL.

FIGURE 3. Amplitude and phase of the coherent reflection (CR) component for $J = 11$ (panels A-1,2) and the component due to perturbation of the nonlinear force (NL) (panels B-1,2). For comparison, dashed lines in panel B-2 show the phases of the CR component depicted in panel A-2. The grey area indicates the range of CEOAEs depicted in Fig. 2. Notice that the dynamic range of the CR and NL components is larger than the overall dynamic range of CEOAEs. The legends indicate the click levels. Notice that as the stimulus intensity increases, the phase slope becomes shallower for the CR and NL components. In contrast, the phase slope of their sum, namely the CEOAE phase depicted in Fig. 2A-2 and represented by the grey area in panels A-2 and B-2, remains nearly level invariant.

agreement with the CR component of SFOAEs. Details are given in the caption of Fig. 2. We chose to shift the CR component because coherent reflection is the primary source in the case of CEOAEs and SFOAEs derived from this cochlear model.

The CR components of CEOAEs and SFOAEs seem to be almost equivalent in the given intensity range. Their growth is approximately linear at the lowest intensities and then saturates. For the CR CEOAE, there is a small decline in amplitude at the highest intensity (65 dB SPL). The NL components of SFOAEs have a slightly larger amplitude than the NL components of CEOAEs, but their growth is the same; i.e. cubic at the lowest intensities. We can see the same decline in the amplitude of the NL CEOAE component at the highest stimulus level. The entire CEOAE I/O function is dominated at the lowest intensities by the CR component but then as the intensity grows it

FIGURE 4. CEOAE (A), CR (B) and NL (C) components in the time-domain compared with SFOAEs. The vertical dotted lines show that the fine structure is almost level invariant. Also, notice the opposite phases of the NL and CR components (the dotted lines are in the same position in all panels). Stimulus intensities in dB are written using blue (for CEOAEs) and red (for SFOAEs) labels.

saturates as the NL component amplitude approaches the CR component. In contrast, SFOAE I/O functions decline at the highest intensities. This decline may be due to the equivalent amplitudes of the CR and NL components. In our previous papers [1, 9], we showed that the phase of the NL component is almost exactly 180 deg. shifted relative to the phase of the CR component. Therefore, the CR and the NL components destructively interfere.

Figure 4 shows transfer functions of CEOAEs (calculated from Figs. 2 and 3) and SFOAEs (taken from [1]) in the frequency range from 1.5 to 3 kHz converted into the time domain by inverse fast Fourier transformation. The transfer functions were obtained by taking the shifted CEOAEs data shown in the I/O functions (Fig. 2B,C,D). At the lowest intensities, SFOAEs and CEOAEs are equivalent. As the intensity grows, the longer latency components of SFOAEs decline faster than the longer-latency components of CEOAEs. This decline is most obvious at about 4-5 ms in Fig. 4A. In contrast, the CR components seem to be very much equivalent in CEOAEs and SFOAEs. Therefore, the NL component is the main cause of the visible differences between CEOAEs and SFOAEs derived from this cochlear model. Notice that the NL component of SFOAE has a larger amplitude in longer-latency components than the NL component of CEOAE. This is most probably the reason why the destructive interference between the CR and NL components removes the longer-latency components in SFOAEs.

CONCLUSION

The analytical solution for SFOAEs presented in [1] for a nonlinear cochlear model was validated for CEOAEs by comparison with numerical results derived from the same model. The solution showed that despite the coherent reflection of the forward-going traveling wave being the primary generation mechanism for SFOAEs and CEOAEs, the reflected wavelets perturb the nonlinear force which generates an additional OAE component [9]. Here, we showed that the OAE component due to coherent reflection (CR) is equivalent across levels for SFOAEs and CEOAEs. In contrast, the components due to perturbation of the nonlinear force (NL) differ. For SFOAEs, the NL component has stronger components with longer latencies than for CEOAEs (see Fig. 4C). The amplitude of the NL component for SFOAEs is larger than for CEOAEs and as the intensity increases, it reaches the amplitude of the CR component (Fig. 2B,C,D). Differences between simulated CEOAEs and SFOAEs shown in the time domain (Fig. 4) are not large. On the other hand, stimulus intensity strongly affects fine-structure amplitude and phase slope of SFOAEs, as shown in [1]. In contrast, the fine-structure amplitude and phase slope of CEOAEs are almost level invariant (Fig. 2A).

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Torsten Marquart]: Interesting! I find it, however, difficult to see physiologically the perturbation of the nonlinear force causing an emission (like a reflection does). Do I understand correctly that this component does not exist without the reflection component? Thus, should one understand it as a correction of the reflection component estimate rather than a component/source itself?

[Václav Vencovský]: Thank you Torsten. The reflected waves perturb the nonlinear force, so you are correct that we do not have this "component" without reflection component. But in this sense, it is similar to the reflection component of distortion-product OAEs, where you do not have a reflection component (secondary) without the distortion component (primary). So I think we can call this component due to perturbation of the nonlinear force a component of OAEs. However, it seems that it is not possible to separate this component due to perturbation from the component due to reflection by, e.g., inverse Fourier transform.

[Torsten Marquart]: Last line, p3. "We chose the CR component because ..." Not clear what you chose it for. You chose the CR to empirically shift to align it with NL? Would it not be a reason to keep CR put and shift NL instead?

[Václav Vencovský]: The reason for the shifting is that we want to compare CEOAEs evoked with clicks in dB peSPL and SFOAEs evoked with tones in dB SPL. There is a large difference between stimulus intensities. Because the CR components of CEOAEs and SFOAEs are almost equivalent, shifting those seems to be reasonable.

[Pim Van Dijk]: This is a very interesting analysis of a model that was presented at the previous MOH meeting. I have only a minor suggestion to improve the presentation. In the caption of Figure 4 you may want to describe what the labels (20/80, etc) in the figures mean. Also, is the vertical axis pressure? Is the unit in Pascals?

[Václav Vencovský]: Thank you Pim. I have adapted the caption. The vertical axis is not in Pascals because the time domain signal derived from the model in so-called artificial units (a.u.) is divided by the input amplitude in Pascals. The blue and red labels are stimulus levels in dB.

Comments after the talk:

[Christopher Bergevin]: What is the rationale for putting the irregularities in the undamping force? Is there any physiological rationale to justify that as oppose to that of putting it somewhere will you still get similar sort of results?

[Václav Vencovský]: If you see images of the organ of Corti, sometimes you see that outer hair cells are not placed regularly. Sometimes you see four rows of outer hair cells. So the main reason for putting irregularities in the undamping term is that amplification in the cochlea may not vary smoothly with position along the basilar membrane. In the not shown simulations, we introduced irregularities into the stiffness and we obtained similar results to those currently presented. So we believe that these results do not depend on the place (term of the BM motion equation) where we put irregularities.

[Julien Meaud]: Do you have some intuition why the nonlinear component is so different between click and pure tone.

[Václav Vencovský]: No, we do not have any explanation for this difference. We have to look more closely at it in the future. We are speculating that the longer latencies in the nonlinear component than in the coherent reflection component of SFOAEs could be due to the micromechanical part of the cochlear model. There is a second array of oscillator which is driven by the BM acceleration, which emphasizes higher frequencies.

[Jont Allen]: Do you think, or do you believe, or accept that roughness is not due to roughness, but it is due to reflections from the BM coming back because the irregularities are pretty high. My view, and I want to know if you agree with this, you got a reflection coming back from a place and you have a signal going in and those are interacting with each other in a strange way. And that is what it gives. So if you get rid of reflection you remove it because of the difference in impedance then you will not see that. Is that reasonable?

[Václav Vencovský]: In our model, if there is no roughness then there will be no reflection and you will not see the perturbation of the nonlinear force.

[Jont Allen]: Looking at very clear regularity of hair cells, it is pretty hard to argue that there is roughness.

[Sunil Puria]: I do not know if you said what percentage of roughness did you introduce. Was it as just Jont said big? How was it?

[Václav Vencovský]: I do not remember the exact value by head, but it was approximately 1%.

[Sunil Puria]: I know that when people introduce this roughness and look what they want to look at in this case SFOAEs, what happens to the basilar membrane response? Is it still smooth?

[Václav Vencovský]: Yes, for this extent of roughness it is smooth.

[Sunil Puria]: Ok, that is a good choice. Thank you.

Correction of the last reply added after the conference:

[Václav Vencovský]: The correct extent of roughness used in the presented simulations is 2%. The BM response for this extent of irregularities is mostly smooth, however, a detailed examination reveals that around the maximal amplitude of the BM response (peak of the traveling wave) the amplitude may vary by about 1 dB.